

About Individual Project Reference Sheets

The Project Reference Sheets summarize a subset of results from the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program 2024 Annual Report. Each Project Reference Sheet provides an at-a-glance overview of the Project, including its hydrology, key nutrient retention results, and any relevant practices (“Enhancement Considerations”) which may increase nutrient retention at that or similar Projects or be considered in future wetland Project site selection. All data were collected by the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program researchers, except for the Duck and Otter Creek Project (data collected by Old Women Creek National Estuarine Research staff) and the Montpelier Wetland Project (data collected by researchers from The Ohio State University). For full results and context, including details on the Project-specific features noted in the “Enhancement Considerations,” see the Project by Project Summaries in Volume 2 of the 2024 Annual Report.

Nutrient filtration and runoff prevention calculations

Nutrient retention results are presented only for Projects with sufficient data for runoff prevention and/or filtration estimates. Nutrient filtration estimates were calculated using individual approaches for each wetland but generally refer to the amount of new phosphorus or new nitrogen that were retained by the wetland. Runoff prevention refers to estimated wetland nutrient retention from the prevention of phosphorus loss due to land use conversion of former agricultural fields. The variation in the phosphorus loss estimates (presented as standard deviation) stems from the variability in typical edge-of-field nutrient loss estimates (Pease et al., 2018). For detailed definitions and nutrient retention estimate calculation methods, see Table 2 in the About this Report section of Volume 1 and Appendix III: Nutrient Budget Calculations in Volume 2, respectively.

Data Disclaimer

The data and management summaries contained in these Project Reference Sheets and the 2024 Annual Report are provisional. Every effort has been made to ensure their correctness. The data is provided as is without warranties of any kind, express or implied. By using this data, the user assumes all risk and agrees that the provider shall not be liable for any loss, damage, or consequences arising from its use. The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program is supported by the Ohio Department of Natural Resources, the Ohio Water Development Authority, U.S. Environmental Protection Agency’s Great Lakes Restoration Initiative, and the Ohio Department of Higher Education’s Harmful Algal Bloom Research Initiative Program. The information, findings, and conclusions in this report are those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the views of the funding organizations. Any use of trade, product, or firm names is for descriptive purposes only and does not imply endorsement by the State of Ohio or U.S. Government. Contact the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program prior to using these data and before citing research and management findings.

Andreoff Project, Wyandot County (40.75722, -83.49430)

Since construction in 2022, the Andreoff Project has functioned as an isolated wetland at which periods of increased rainfall can cause surface runoff from the surrounding fields to drain into the pool, which then drains into an adjacent ditch when it reaches maximum capacity. However, this intermittent outflow has only been qualitatively observed by researchers and would require drainage area calculations and the installation of a flume to accommodate collection of outflow samples to assess the Project's nutrient filtration function. The main depressional pool retains water during most of the year even under prolonged drought conditions.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 278 acres of restored wetland and consists of a single 1.5-acre wetland pool without designed inflows or outflows. The pool receives surface runoff from the surrounding landscape and largely functions as an isolated wetland. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as an event where the site receives runoff.

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar isolated wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Installing a flume or a water level control structure would allow water to exit the Main Pool at a set location and give researchers a set point to determine the nutrient concentration at this intermittent outflow.
- Assess parcel footprint for the ability to capture tile drain, stream, or ditch water inputs, in addition to precipitation, in order to optimize nutrient input potential (i.e., connectivity).

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Blanchard River Project, Putnam County (41.02700, -84.05100)

Since construction in 2020, the Blanchard River Project, which was intended to allow the Blanchard River to overflow into a diversion channel, has rarely received water through its designed inflow because its elevation can only be reached under extremely high flow conditions. Instead, it is fed by backflow entering through the lower elevation designed outflow.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 27 acres of restored wetland, consisting of a floodplain channel and a series of isolated vernal pools between the floodplain channel and the river. During storm events the Blanchard River rises to flood its banks into the diversion channel before reconnecting with the Blanchard River downstream. During ambient conditions, the Blanchard River will backflow into the diversion channel from the lower portion of the channel. The isolated vernal pools only receive flood water during record flows and do not hold water for long. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm in which the Blanchard River floods its banks into the diversion channel.

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar floodplain wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Improvements to the lower portion of the channel would facilitate retention and filtering of the backflow entering the outlet from the river year-round (i.e., consider implementing a means of controlling flow entering/exiting at River Lower).
- Planting vegetation along the banks of the lower channel would be more beneficial to nutrient uptake than the large rock that currently lines the banks, further promoting the floodplain function of that portion of the Project.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Bright Wetland Project, Hancock County (41.01800, -83.55700)

Since construction in 2023, the Bright Wetland Project has largely functioned as intended, with its pools capturing and retaining tile inflows and surface runoff from surrounding agricultural land. Only minor design setbacks related to outflow limit the nutrient retention of the Project.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed, with the outflow having two Agri Drain water level control structures that discharge to the Blanchard River from Pools 1 and 2. The Project has 8.5 acres of restored wetland, consisting of four wetland pools. Pools 1 and 2 receive tile inflow from up gradient agricultural fields, while Pools 3 and 4 receive surface runoff from an agricultural field on the southern border of the Project. Pool 4 overflows into Pool 3, which overflows into Pool 2. During high flows of > 1000 cubic feet per second (cfs) the adjacent Blanchard River floods the wetland. A hydrologic event at this Project defined as a storm event in which the flow of Blanchard River is > 1000 cfs and floods the wetland.

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similarly designed wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- The water control feature in Pool 1 (WCF 1) allows backflow from the Blanchard River into the pool during high flow events. Increasing the level of the stoplogs would prevent backflow into Pool 1 while increasing connectivity between Pool 1 and Existing Wetland 1 to the south, allowing nutrient retention opportunity. Raising the stoplogs would also eliminate the possibility of WCF 1 acting as an inflow during high flow events, helping to solidify researchers' understanding of Project hydrology while ensuring the Project captures water as intended.
- A low section of the walking path berm that surrounds Pool 2 has been allowing surface water to bypass the Pool 2 water control feature (WCF 2) and flow to the Blanchard River. Increasing the height of the low section of Pool 2 berm would allow water to flow through the water control feature as designed, increasing residence time within the pool. *Note:* ODNR engineers are aware of the low berm issue in Pool 2 and are making alteration plans to increase berm height.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Brooks Park Project, Fairfield County (39.90057, -82.51620)

Since construction in 2021, the Brooks Park Project's main nutrient benefit has been filtering inflows from Murphy's Run, as well as occasional backflow from Buckeye Lake. In 2024, this Project acted as a nutrient sink for the large inflow volume it captured from Murphy's Run, filtering 11.4 lbs phosphorus per acre. However, the overall nutrient benefit of the Project could be improved by relatively simple design modifications.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is mixed in terms of management. The Project (5 acres of restored wetland) is a flow-through wetland, nuanced by periodic backflow from Buckeye Lake. Water enters from Murphy's Run via a solar-powered pump (maintained, though not actively managed, by a state park staff) or passively through a separate inlet location. The water resides in wetland pools that permanently/seasonally flood before reaching the outflow into Buckeye Lake. There is often backflow from Buckeye Lake into the wetland pools during the summer when the water level in the lake is raised. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as an event in which Murphy's Run stream discharge is greater than 1.55 cubic feet per second. At this threshold, Murphy's Run flows into the wetland. The water level threshold at which Buckeye Lakes backflows into the wetland pools is 889.5 ft, a number inferred based on elevation information in the Project design plans.

Nutrient Retention

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar pumped, flow-through wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Maximizing the volume of water that enters the West Pool via pump would increase residence time at the Project and resulting nutrient filtration opportunity.
- Installing a more efficient pump would bring in greater water volume, as researchers have observed the current solar-powered pump moving little to no water.
- Additionally, installing a cement wall between the Main Pool and the Mid-wetland Stream to divert water from the Main Pool to the West Pool before it flows back into the Mid-Wetland Stream would slow down flows from Murphy's Run, increasing residence time of water in the wetland pools and resulting nutrient filtration opportunity. This design modification would still allow for Buckeye Lake backflows to be treated during times of high-water elevation.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Buehler Farms Project, Sandusky County

Since construction in 2021, the nutrient retention and hydrologic regime of the Buehler Farms Project have been unclear. Soils at this Project have capacity to sorb phosphate, suggesting potential for retention of any received phosphorus loads. However, researchers have not been informed when, or if, the property owner pumps water into the wetland from the ditch despite multiple requests for this information. If the Project is not pumping from the inflow ditch, or during low flow conditions, then there is a missed opportunity to capture nutrients before flowing into Muddy Creek and Sandusky Bay.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is actively managed. The Project has 40 acres of restored wetland, consisting of a coastal diked wetland pool that receives water from a ditch adjacent to the pool through a control structure. The ditch appears to be a mix of tile drain runoff from adjacent agricultural fields and is connected to Little Muddy Creek through culverts under the road. There are two water control structures at this Project, one is near the intake pump and the other connects to Little Muddy Creek. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as an event when water is let into or out of the site through a water level control structure.

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar coastal diked wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- If pumping occurred from the ditch during conditions with increased nutrient levels and was then held in the Project pool before entering Sandusky Bay, the Project could have a greater impact on nutrient reduction.

Lack of information about pumped inputs limits the understanding that can be gained from this Project. As a result, the Monitoring Program does not plan to collect new data at this Project in 2025.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Burntwood-Langenkamp Project, Mercer County (40.50103, -84.59570)

Since construction in 2022, the Burntwood-Langenkamp Project’s main nutrient benefit has been filtering actively pumped and passive inflows occurring at high flows from Burntwood Creek. A design modification adding a sump pit (hole in front of the pump to allow greater water volumes) was made in 2024 to increase flow volume and succeeded in more than doubling the inflow as compared to 2023. The Project’s active management and pump-driven system moderated potential drought impacts in 2024, and the Project filtered 8.9 lbs phosphorus per acre, in addition to its runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source contributing 0.6 lbs phosphorus per acre each year.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this flow-through Project is actively managed. The Project has 27 acres of restored wetland. Water enters from Burntwood Creek via a pump (managed by ODNR staff) or via the inflow notch when water reaches a certain threshold. The water resides in a pool or flows through a sinuous path between various pools before reaching the outflow into Coldwater Creek, at which there is a water level control structure that can be manually adjusted. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm in which Burntwood Creek flow reaches 27 cubic feet per second, as this is when researchers estimate the creek flows through the inflow notch.

Nutrient Retention

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar actively managed flow-through wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Digging of sump to allow water to be pumped into the wetland for longer durations doubled the total inflow of water treated by the Project.
- Modifications to create more shallow, slow-flow habitat with longer residence time would increase the capacity of the wetland to retain nutrients through vegetation by expanding the available area for wetland plants to establish.
- Active hydrologic management can moderate potential drought impacts by ensuring large hydrologic events are captured and held. Pump-driven systems can also perform this function, mechanically facilitating water/nutrient inputs even when water levels in the creek are below the threshold for the inflow notch.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Clary-Boulee-McDonald Project, Seneca County (41.23139, -83.26845)

Since construction in 2021, the Clary-Boulee-McDonald Project’s primary known nutrient benefit has been its runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source, preventing 0.6 lbs phosphorus export per acre each year. Otherwise, the Project has functioned as a passively managed floodplain of Wolf Creek, though water inputs to this Project were limited due to drought conditions in 2024. These conditions limited opportunity both for nutrient retention and for researchers to assess trends in water quality and relationships between the Project’s pools, as many were dry during sampling visits. Soils do have capacity to sorb phosphate if and when water and nutrient inputs are received to the Project.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has a total of 45 acres restored wetland and is bisected by Wolf Creek, a segment of the Sandusky River. The northern portion of the Project consists of a wetland pool, swale and wet meadow. During high flow, Wolf Creek floods its banks into the swale and Pool 3. The southern portion of the wetland consists of wet meadows and two wetland pools. During high flow, Wolf Creek also floods its banks and flows into the pools via cut banks. During dry periods, Pool 1 rarely holds water while Pool 2 holds water year-round. All three pools additionally receive surface runoff from the surrounding wet meadows. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event in which Wolf Creek floods its banks and delivers water to the wetland pools.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmfield Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
45 acres	0.6 lbs	103 ± 70 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar floodplain wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Pool 1 is designed to capture larger storm events from Wolf Creek but primarily receives surface water from the surrounding Project area wet meadow. Lowering the berms between Wolf Creek and Pool 1 could increase the water connectivity between these two features during smaller storm events throughout the year, which could help to increase the nutrient retention potential of Pool 1.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Darby Project, Ottawa County (41.53431, -83.00600)

Since construction in 2021, the nutrient benefit of the Darby Project has been limited due to tradeoffs in management goals. Water level management at this Project prioritizes seasonal wildlife habitat needs, generally by adding water to wetland pools in the fall and draining them in the spring. From 2022-2024, the Project's two major pools were kept permanently inundated, but water levels fluctuated in both in response to seasonal patterns in management activities. Water chemistry data suggest periods of connection with LaCarpe Creek and the adjacent ditch when water level control structures (WLCSs) were left open in the late spring, allowing some nutrient-rich water to be received and filtered by the wetland pools. However, water chemistry data also indicate a lack of connectivity during key spring flows and other instances of high nutrient load.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is actively managed. This coastal Project has 352 acres of restored wetland featuring two major pools: a large western pool (Pool 1) and a smaller eastern pool (Pool 4). The Project receives water from a ditch that runs adjacent to Pools 1 and 4, as well as LaCarpe Creek that flows from south to north along the west side of the wetland. There are three WLCSs along LaCarpe Creek and the adjacent ditch, connecting them to Pools 1 and 4. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as an event where WLCSs are open, and water can flow into or out of Pools 1 and 4.

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar coastal wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Promote increased nutrient filtration opportunity by “cycling” LaCarpe Creek water through the wetland pools once or a few times per year, especially by allowing water to enter the wetland in spring when nutrient sequestration is most impactful for preventing harmful algal blooms in nearby Lake Erie.

Project site restrictions (e.g., access to federal wildlife to reserve), barriers to access (e.g., dike conditions and hunting activity), and complex flow paths, as well as incomplete knowledge about water levels within the wetland units, limit the understanding that can be gained from this Project. As a result, sampling frequency by the Monitoring Program will decrease in 2025.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Duck and Otter Creek Project, Lucas County (41.67031, -83.47613)

Since construction in June 2023, the main nutrient benefit of the Duck and Otter Creek Project has been slowing flow and filtering water from Duck Creek. Surface water nutrient concentration estimates suggest that the Project wetland is functioning as a sink for phosphorus and has had a small and more variable influence on reducing nitrogen concentrations; however, flow measurements are needed to validate these conclusions. A reduction in water levels since construction, either due to drought conditions over 2024 or the re-grading of the site that occurred during construction to slow flow and increase water retention, suggests that the Project has the potential to retain and treat greater volumes of water. Future measurements of water flow at the monitoring stations are needed to evaluate nutrient load reductions for the Project.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this coastal flowthrough Project is passively managed. The Project has 10.56 acres of restored or created wetland and features several wetland pools situated along reconfigured meandering natural stream channel. Water enters from Duck Creek upstream and flows slowly through the Project before outflowing to Duck Creek downstream.

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in similar isolated wetland projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Assess potential for directing additional water inputs to the Project in order to optimize nutrient input potential (i.e., connectivity).
- Consider expanding the footprint of the Project by implementing additional components of the planned floodplain wetland restoration and stream channel naturalization projects along Duck and Otter Creeks.

Current monitoring data based on concentrations alone suggest that the wetland is retaining some phosphorus and relatively less nitrogen; however, flow measurements are needed to reliably assess the volume of water treated and, therefore, nutrient load. Additionally, no significant high-flow events have been sampled for the Project, and event-based storm sampling should be prioritized during subsequent monitoring to characterize the wetland's nutrient retention and loading over a larger range of hydrological regimes.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Forder Bridge Project, Paulding County (41.21932, -84.67270)

Since construction in 2021, the main nutrient benefit of the Forder Bridge Project has been filtering nutrients delivered from a culvert (tile drain). The whole parcel drains an agricultural field (7.3 acres), forested plot (6.2 acres), and residential area (1 acre). Nutrient retention estimates were improved in 2024 by communication with local partners with a better understanding of the drainage area of the site. The culvert-fed flow-through treatment train is the main contributor to new nutrient retention, whereas the river-adjacent pools flooded only one or two times in 2023 and 2024. The Project filtered 1.5 lbs phosphorus per acre in 2024, in addition to the runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source (0.7 lbs phosphorus per acre each year). The vegetation nutrient stock at this Project was 111 lbs phosphorus per acre for aboveground and 4.5 lbs phosphorus per acre for belowground biomass.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology of this Project is passively managed. The Project has 5 acres of restored wetland, including multiple wetland features: a culvert-fed treatment train (Complex 4), elevated pools adjacent to the Maumee River (Complex 2), and sets of depressional pools fed only by surface water (Complexes 1 and 3). Water from land southeast of the Project enters the treatment train from a culvert during storm events. Each treatment train pool passively flows into the next and eventually into a small stream that delivers water to the Maumee River. The elevated riverbank pools and the depressional pools primarily receive water from only surface runoff. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event in which flow is expected through the culvert that feeds the treatment train.

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar tile-fed and treatment train wetlands or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Diverting water from the treatment train and/or the Maumee into the disconnected depressional pools (Complexes 1-3) could increase the capacity for nutrient removal, but the elevation of these features in comparison to the Maumee River would likely make this prohibitively costly.
- It is important to accurately assess connectivity to water and nutrient sources by engaging in dialogue with on-the-ground local experts to estimate drainage area, in addition to using available tools like USGS StreamStats.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Fruth Wetland Project, Seneca County (41.13147, -83.36540)

Since construction in 2021, the primary known nutrient benefit of the Fruth Wetland Project has been its runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient, preventing 0.7 lbs phosphorus export per acre each year. Otherwise, the Project has operated as an isolated depressional wetland. Precipitation events and seasonal groundwater table fluctuations are the primary hydrologic drivers at this Project. This lack of direct system inputs and outputs likely limited both the nutrient inputs to the Project and the ability of researchers to assess the nutrient benefit of this Project. Soils have capacity to sorb phosphate if and when water and nutrient inputs are received to the Project.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology of this Project is passively managed. The Project has 10 acres of restored wetland and consists of four wetland pools that connect to Wolf Creek in the southeast via shallow groundwater. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event in which the depressional pools receive runoff.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmfield Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
10 acres	0.7 lbs	12 ± 8 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar isolated wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Expanding the amount of stormwater runoff the Project receives by increasing either connection to upland drainage or connection to subsurface tile drainage on the southern border of the Project could improve its nutrient retention potential.
- Consider improvements such as allowing direct tile inflow from the southern bordering field or digging the pools deeper to increase groundwater connectivity. These alterations would allow more input to Pool 1 following storm events and for Pool 1 to retain water for a greater portion of the year, as well as allowing researchers to collect more water samples from this location.
- Assess parcel footprint for the ability to capture tile drain, stream, or ditch water inputs, in addition to precipitation, to optimize nutrient input potential (i.e., connectivity).

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Indian Creek Project, Butler County

Since construction in 2024, the nutrient benefit of the Indian Creek Project has likely been minimal. As one of the few true forested wetlands in the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program, this Project could have provided unique insight if it were more connected to the watershed. However, data from monitoring beginning in August 2024 suggest no inflow from Indian Creek to the wetland occurred, and data from years preceding monitoring indicate that even in wetter years the wetland would receive only limited stream water and nutrient inputs due to its design.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 13 acres of restored wetland, consisting of three designed flow paths. Water is intended to enter via Indian Creek overflows (forest flow path, riverside flow path), as well as by adjacent field tile inflow. Water exits by surface and/or subsurface connection to Indian Creek. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as Indian Creek reaching a stage of 3.2 ft.

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar forested wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Both the wetland pools and the marginally more hydrologically connected floodplain shelf were constructed at a height that severely limits inflows to this Project. Modifications to increase connectivity and lower the threshold for inflows would increase nutrient retention potential.
- Since the elevation is too high for creek flows, a limitation which could be assessed in site-selection and design of future Projects using existing datasets (elevation and USGS stream flow), researchers suggest leaning more into subsurface and surface agricultural nonpoint runoff and guiding those flows through the whole Project by capturing the main field tile sooner and directing flow through constructed flow paths.

A near complete lack of water and nutrient inputs limits the understanding that can be gained from this Project. As a result, new data collection by the Monitoring Program in 2025 will be limited to annual soil sampling.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Magee Marsh Project, Ottawa County (41.60535, -83.15250)

Since construction in 2021, the nutrient benefit of the Magee Marsh Project has been limited due to tradeoffs in management goals. Water level management at this Project prioritizes seasonal wildlife habitat needs, generally flooding the wetland pool in the fall and draining it in the spring. However, for optimal nutrient retention, it may be more beneficial to fill the wetland pool in the spring, when there are larger nutrient runoff loads in the source creek water. Additionally, in both 2024 and 2023, the Project was kept isolated from the source creek water and drained for infrastructure improvements throughout the wetland complex. In 2024, the Project received water only once for a period of 10 days (a total of 149 million liters) and retained 0.2 lbs of phosphorus per acre.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is actively managed and has one distinct feature: a large (~ 170 acre) wetland pool that is connected to the adjacent Turtle Creek in two locations. Water enters from Turtle Creek at the western portion of the pool via one water level control structure (WLCS) and exits at the eastern portion of the pool via another WLCS. In the northwestern portion of the pool, a third WLCS allows water to flow into a canal to the north where it can then flow into a non-H2Ohio pool or Turtle Creek. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as an adjustment of a WLCS that alters water flow speed and/or direction into or out of the wetland pool.

Nutrient Retention

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar coastal wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future Project site selection:

- Promote more frequent filling events in spring, when nutrient sequestration is most impactful for preventing harmful algal blooms in nearby Lake Erie.

As construction within the Project concludes and typical management activities resume, different nutrient retention patterns may emerge, though the tradeoffs between habitat- and nutrient-driven water level management will remain. More accurate nutrient retention estimates for future years can be facilitated by prompt notification of WLCS actions allowing timely sampling of hydrologic events, as well as information on the fate of pumped water.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Maumee River Floodplain Project, Henry County (41.41480, -84.03070)

Since construction in 2023, the Maumee River Floodplain (also known as Rotary Riverside Preserve Restoration) Project’s primary known nutrient benefit has been its runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source, preventing approximately 0.8 lbs phosphorus export per acre each year. Low rainfall conditions in 2024 likely limited the newly delivered nutrients to the Project, which limits the total capacity for the Project to filter and retain nutrients. However, the Project functions as a floodplain wetland in wetter conditions and can even receive extensive seasonal flooding, as researchers observed during an initial site visit in early 2023, suggesting potential for meaningful nutrient inputs in future years.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 35 acres of restored wetland and consists of a single large central wetland, three northern pools of varying depths (one of which was constructed to meet habitat needs of a specific endangered fish), and many hummock-hollow pools in the southwest area. The large central wetland acts as an occasional floodplain pool. The smaller pools normally act as depressional wetlands but also receive water from the Maumee or existing oxbow wetland at very high water levels. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event in which the Maumee River floods the central pool via the existing oxbow wetland.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmland Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
35 acres	0.8 lbs	46 ± 26 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in similar floodplain wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Enlarging the central wetland pool would increase the Project’s holding capacity for water and ensure that nutrient rich water does not leave the site.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Mercer Wetland Project, Mercer County (40.49830, -84.56846)

Since construction in 2022, the main nutrient benefit of the Mercer Wetland Project has been filtration of inflows pumped from Grand Lake St. Marys. Nutrient concentrations throughout the Project suggest nutrient retention occurring within both Phase 1 and 2 overall. However, particulate matter enters Phase 2 (western portion) seasonally from the forested wetland pool, rendering that portion of the Project a source of total phosphorus on an annual scale. Due to the active management style of the Project and its inflow pump, drought conditions in 2024 would not have had a large role in nutrient filtration associated with the Project.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology of this Project is actively managed by ODNR staff. The Project has 29.7 acres of restored wetland, featuring two treatment trains (one per each phase) with a pump and multiple water level control structures (WLCS). In Phase 1, water is pumped in from Grand Lake St. Marys through a series of tiles under a corn field and into one of two shallow wetland pools, directed by WLCS. In Phase 2, water is pumped in from Grand Lake St. Marys into a pool. In both phases, water level in all pools and flow between pools is controlled using WLCS. Both phases are managed in a “raise and rest” type of style, in which the wetland pools are pumped full in early spring each year and refilled when water levels begin to drop, resulting in wetland pools that are permanently flooded year-round through the combined inputs from pumping and surface runoff events associated with heavy rains. The pump does not run during the winter. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as any time the pump is turned on or the Project receives 0.5” or more of rain.

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar treatment train wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- To increase nutrient retention across the Project, the inflow pump for both phases should run more often to increase the hydraulic loading rate (volume of wetland inflow per wetland acres, HLR). An increase in HLR is often correlated with higher nutrient reduction rates, depending on the functionality of other aspects of the wetland (e.g., soil sorption, vegetation uptake).
- Another way to increase nutrient retention across both phases would be to seed/reseed Pool 2 in Phase 1 (second pool from the north in Phase 1) and all pools in Phase 2. Despite the Project operating for 1.5 years, no wetland plants have started to grow in these locations. It is possible the water in Pool 2 of Phase 1 is too deep for wetland plants to establish. If that is the case, the inflow pump would have to be turned off for an appropriate amount of time for vegetation to grow. While this would reduce the HLR in the short-term while plants become established, it could increase the Project’s potential nutrient retention in the long-term.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Montpelier Wetland Project, Williams County

Since construction in 2023, the capacity of soils to sorb phosphate remained similar from year to year at the Montpelier Wetland Project, indicating a potential for soil nutrient retention. The impact of the Project's phosphorus filter is being evaluated by affiliate researchers, who also collect water samples and estimated nutrient filtration at this Project¹. Though the dry conditions throughout 2024 likely limited its overall efficacy, the Project filtered 2.8 lbs phosphorus per acre. Its runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source also prevents approximately 0.3 lbs phosphorus export per acre each year.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has approximately 8.5 acres of restored wetland and consists of a southern wetland with a flow-through wetland system, and a northern wetland with a series of small depressional wetlands. The southern wetland receives water through a tile outlet on the eastern side and outlets into an underground phosphorus filter which outflows into a ditch, while the northern wetland receives water from surface runoff. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event in which the eastern tile delivers water to the flow-through wetland system.

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- No considerations to report at this time. Affiliate researchers are analyzing surface water for nutrient concentration. The Monitoring Program will support data interpretation where possible. The results of evaluation of the function of the phosphorus filter in this Project will help to indicate the potential benefit of this type of facility for enhancing wetland performance, especially as the southwest wetland is receiving water from a legacy-phosphorus field which is expected to deliver high phosphorus concentration.

¹ Stoltzfus, Brooker, and Martin, Unpublished Results, 2025

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

North Ridge Project, Ottawa County

Since construction in 2021, the nutrient benefit of the North Ridge Project has been stewarded by the private property owner actively managing the water level control structures (WLCSs) at the Project. Communication mechanisms for tracking WLCS changes improved in 2024 in order to prepare for an estimate of surface water nutrient filtration. For now, researchers estimate that this Project’s runoff prevention conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source also prevents approximately 0.7 lbs phosphorus export per acre each year.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology of this Project is actively managed. This Project has 23 acres of restored wetland consisting of three wetland pools: Center, East, and West. Water inputs come from tile drainage in the farm field to the north flowing into the “L” shaped ditch around the wetland site. The pump at the southern point of the ditch pumps ditch water into the wetland pools. Water outflows from the Project through a WLCS to Packer Creek. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a pumping event where water is actively pumped from the drainage ditch into the wetland pools.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmfield Area	Total Phosphorus Runoff Prevention	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
23 acres	0.7 lbs	20 ± 13 lbs

Enhancement

Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar actively managed and/or formerly agricultural wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Create pump infrastructure and plan active management that balances water input volumes with residence time to maximize nutrient input and filtration potential.
- Assess parcels for consistent connection to nutrient-laden water inputs (e.g., tile drainage) to maintain consistent opportunity for nutrient retention.

Improved understanding of nutrient retention at this Project will rely on sampling during hydrologic events and collecting data on measurement of flow through the agricultural pump, requiring timely notification of pump actions. These efforts are supported by iteratively improving open communication between property managers and researchers.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Oak Openings Preserve Project, Lucas County (41.58036, -83.86780)

Since construction in 2021, the Oak Openings Preserve Project’s primary known nutrient benefit has been its runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source, preventing approximately 0.5 lbs phosphorus export per acre each year. The nutrient filtration and overall wetland function of this Project was likely limited under dry climatic conditions in 2024, though several pools held 10 – 20 cm of water throughout the year. The sources of water to this Project and the effect of its sandy soils remain unclear and limit complete understanding of its impact.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 22 acres of restored wetland, consisting of 15 wetland pools that are arranged into four main flow paths. All four flow paths receive water from surface runoff, and they all drain into the same stream-seep wetland outlet that flows into a nearby stream. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event in which the flow paths receive surface runoff.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmfield Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
22 acres	0.5 lbs	26 ± 13 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar isolated wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Assess soil texture to inform prediction of the Project’s capacity to hold water/nutrients and/or indicate connection to groundwater.
- Assess parcel footprint for the ability to capture tile drain, stream, or ditch water inputs, in addition to precipitation, in order to optimize nutrient input potential (i.e., connectivity).

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Oakwoods Projects East and West, Hancock County (41.02400, -83.69600)

Since construction in 2021, the Oakwoods Projects’ capacity for nutrient filtration has been limited by minimal watershed connection, resulting in little water or nutrient input to the majority of wetland pools. In 2024, even the pool intended to act as a floodplain received essentially no input, as Aurand Run did not flood sufficiently high. Additionally, tile drains connected to select pools may be clogged, limiting inputs from adjacent agricultural fields. As a result, the primary nutrient benefit of these Projects thus far has been the runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source (a combined 1.1 lbs phosphorus per acre each year). The vegetation nutrient stock at Oakwoods West Project was 413 lbs phosphorus per acre aboveground and 36 lbs phosphorus per acre belowground.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology of Oakwoods East (right) and West (left) is passively managed. Oakwoods East has 20 acres of restored wetland including four depressional pools connected to subsurface tile drains and 20 isolated depressional pools that are primarily precipitation-fed. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm in which some pools overflow and intermix. Oakwoods West has 30 acres of restored wetland including a water level control structure–equipped pool adjacent to Aurand Run that occasionally floods and 18 other depressional pools that are primarily surface runoff–fed. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm in which flow is expected to flood the pool adjacent to Aurand Run.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmland Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
50 acres	1.1 lbs	117 ± 65 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar formerly agricultural wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- While modifications may enhance Oakwoods’ connection to Aurand Run, the potential nutrient filtration benefit may be constrained by the low nutrient loads delivered by Aurand Run.
- Account for the prevention of nutrient loading from converting formerly agricultural parcels to wetlands (i.e., surface runoff and subsurface drainage prevention).
- Assess parcel for the ability to capture tile drain, stream, or ditch water inputs, in addition to precipitation, in order to optimize nutrient input potential (i.e., connectivity).

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Otsego Schools Project, Wood County (41.42400, -83.74100)

Since construction in 2021, the Otsego Schools Project’s primary known nutrient benefit has been its runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source (approximately 0.7 lbs phosphorus per acre each year). The Project’s connection to the watershed is limited, particularly under the dry conditions of 2024, though its soils do have moderate capacity to sorb phosphorus inputs if received. Future sampling to capture hydrologic events will help researchers assess the extent of the floodplain function of the emergent wetland and estimate any resulting nutrient transport reduction. The wetland at this Project has been extensively used for educational purposes.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 6 acres of restored wetland and consists of a depressional pool complex. There are two emergent wetland pools at the north end that rarely flood, a deep vernal pool in the southwest of the site, and numerous small hummock-hollow pools throughout the southern portion of the site. The site receives water from surface water runoff and typically does not flow out through a defined outflow. The emergent pools receive water from Tontogany Creek when water level rises. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event that causes surface water runoff within the site and raises water level in Tontogany Creek to flood-stage.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmfield Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
6 acres	0.7 lbs	11 ± 11 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar isolated wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Assess parcel footprint for the ability to capture tile drain, stream, or ditch water inputs, in addition to precipitation, in order to optimize nutrient input potential (i.e., connectivity).

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Ottawa NWR Project, Lucas County (41.63663, -83.21500)

Since construction in 2021, the nutrient benefit of the Ottawa NWR Project has been limited due to tradeoffs in management goals. Water level management at this Project prioritizes seasonal wildlife habitat needs, generally by adding water to wetland pools in the fall and draining them in the spring. Water was fully removed from the southern half of the Project (MS5) from May to September of 2024 for dike maintenance and water level control structures (WLCSs) were kept closed, isolating the permanently inundated Pool 3 and further restricting nutrient filtration opportunity.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is actively managed. This Project has 586 acres of restored wetland, and its hydrologic features consist of a northern portion (Pool 3) and a southern portion (MS5), separated by Veler Road and its adjacent ditch. Ditch water flows west to east and can enter the northern and southern portions of the wetland complex through WLCSs. Water is released back into Veler Ditch or out into Crane Creek (ultimately outflowing directly to Lake Erie) during overflow events or in instances where water level is higher in the wetlands and the WLCS gates are opened. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as an overflow event where water flows between the wetland units and Veler Ditch after WLCSs are opened.

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar coastal wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Promote increased nutrient filtration opportunity by “cycling” nutrient-rich water from the source (i.e., Veler Ditch) through the wetland once or a few times per year, especially during the spring when nutrient sequestration is most impactful for preventing harmful algal blooms in Lake Erie.

As typical management activities resume following 2024 construction, different nutrient retention patterns may emerge, though the tradeoffs between habitat- and nutrient-driven water level management will remain. More accurate nutrient retention estimates for future years can be facilitated by prompt notification of WLCS actions allowing timely sampling of hydrologic events.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Redhorse Bend Project, Sandusky County (41.36625, -83.10390)

Since construction in 2021, the constrained floodplain connection design of the Redhorse Bend Project has limited its capacity to receive water and retain nutrients. River water inflows through the streambank cuts only during extreme high flow events of >12,000 cubic feet per second (cfs). Inflow during typical high flow events (8,000–10,000 cfs) is restricted to the eastern ditch. In 2024, these design limitations were exacerbated by drought conditions, resulting in lower nutrient filtration in 2024 than in 2023, along with the Project's runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 55 acres restored wetland with two distinct features: a set of floodplain wetland pools that connect to each other in series but have limited connectivity to water inputs from the river itself; and a single pool meant to capture separate ditch water. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event in which the USGS gage (Sandusky River near Fremont OH - 04198000) reaches 12,000 cfs, as this is when researchers estimate the river flows through the cut banks into the set of floodplain wetland pools. However, when the Sandusky River reaches a lower flow threshold of 3,000 cfs, water first enters a ditch and then the series of minor pools. At another location, a single pool intended to capture water from a separate drainage ditch, in fact, mostly receives inputs from rainwater and surface water runoff from an adjacent meadow.

Nutrient Retention

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar floodplain wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Lower the berm between Pool 6 and the partner-managed highway drainage ditch. Or, if connectivity between the ditch and pool cannot be improved, a location closer to the river might be an alternative to Pool 6 to capture more upland wet meadow drainage.
- Make the ABC pools deeper, with lower berms between them and the main pools, to increase the functionality of the Project by increasing overall site hydrologic connectivity, stormwater storage, and nutrient storage capacity for flooding events rather than just precipitation events.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Sandusky River Headwaters Project, Crawford County (40.79270, -82.79070)

Since construction in 2020, this Project has functioned as a flow-through wetland that increases both storage and nutrient filtration opportunity of water that, prior to construction, would have flowed directly into the Sandusky River from upland agricultural land. Although the two wetland portions of the Project (East and West) have different design characteristics, their unique features contribute to similar water holding capacity and resulting nutrient retention opportunity overall, a balance which intentional land management can further facilitate. The Project’s known nutrient benefit also includes runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source, preventing 0.6 lbs of phosphorus export per acre each year.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 7 acres of restored wetland, consisting of two main wetland pools (East and West) and a series of small vernal pools. Flow from the primary inflow stream originates from an agricultural field and flows to the Project area through forested hillside before it splits between the east and west wetlands. After flowing through the East and West Wetlands, water flows into the Sandusky River. The East Wetland additionally contains a wet meadow, as well as six vernal pools that only receive surface runoff. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event in which flow is delivered from the inflow stream to the East and West Wetlands.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmfield Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
7 acres	0.6 lbs	24 ± 16 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar flow-through wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Regularly clear debris at the East and West Wetland diversion point to increase flow to ensure both wetlands are functioning as efficiently as possible. Currently, more flow has been directed into the East Wetland than the West Wetland due to naturally occurring damming at the diversion point. These flow imbalances may limit optimal opportunity for nutrient retention by vegetation and soils in the West Wetland.
- Move the mounds to the other side of the vernal pools to capture more water. Currently, the vernal pools in the wet meadow portion of the East Wetland rarely hold water from upland drainage due to surface water redirection from the placement of spoils upgradient from the pools.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Springcreek Project, Miami County (40.06820, -84.21191)

Since construction in 2021, the main nutrient benefit of the Springcreek Project has been filtering inflows from Spring Creek and the Great Miami River. However, the nutrient filtration capacity of this Project has been limited by the dry weather conditions of 2023 and 2024 decreasing annual stream flows. Each year there were only two offloading events to the wetlands, which resulted in filtration of 4.8 lbs phosphorus per acre in 2023 and 1.6 lbs phosphorus per acre in 2024. The Project also contributes 0.8 lbs phosphorus per acre each year from runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field to a nutrient source. In 2024, the total retention was 2.5 lbs phosphorus per acre (1.6 + 0.8)

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project (25 acres of restored wetland) is an off-channel wetland consisting of two wetland pools that are connected to one-another by a channel. The North Pool exchanges water with Spring Creek, while the South Pool exchanges water with the Great Miami River. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as an event in which the Great Miami River and Spring Creek flood the wetland pools, possible at discharges of at least 5,229 cubic feet per second (cfs) and 203 cfs, respectively.

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar off-channel wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Lower the Great Miami River inflow notch would allow for more connectivity but less storage capacity during very high flow events, such that a balance would need to be found between capturing high and low flow events while also retaining water long enough for nutrient reductions to occur.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

St. Joseph Confluence Project, Williams County (41.64808, -84.56440)

Since construction in 2021, the St. Joseph Confluence Project’s primary known nutrient benefit has been its runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source, preventing approximately 0.2 lbs phosphorus export per acre each year. Though the dry conditions in 2024 limited the water and nutrients inputs to the Project, the capacity of soils to sorb phosphate suggests potential to capture relatively large loads of phosphorus if and when received. However, there is no active water level management, and the only major water sources for this Project are the adjacent branches of the St. Joseph River. Most pools at this Project function as floodplain wetlands only briefly (a few days or less) when the branches of the St. Joseph River flood. Otherwise, they hold relatively little water and serve as geographically isolated pools. This Project presents a unique opportunity to compare the nutrient reduction benefit and cost efficiency of converting two different land uses—agricultural and Conservation Reserve Program lands—to wetlands.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 31 acres of restored wetland, consisting of a northern and a southern pool complex. There are eight wetland pools plus one oxbow wetland, all of which receive flow from surface water runoff throughout the year, and act as floodplain pools when the St. Joseph River branches overflow their banks. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event where the St. Joseph River exceeds its banks and flows into the pools.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmfield Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
20 acres	0.2 lbs	27 ± 13 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- The pools at this Project are predominantly built to be quite shallow. Modifications for deeper pools could increase residence time and overall nutrient retention.
- Increasing floodplain wetland connection to the river in terms of number of flood events or volume of water received would potentially increase the nutrient retention function of this land.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

St. Joseph's Restoration Project, Williams County (41.64808, -84.56440)

Since construction in 2021, researchers infer that the St. Joseph's Restoration Project has high nutrient retention potential due to the high concentration inputs it receives from agricultural drainage (up to 1.1 mg P/L). However, nutrients are primarily delivered during flooding events, so drought in 2024 and 2023 limited nutrient delivery. This Project's largest pool (B) experiences periods of low oxygen and high phosphorus concentrations. Current phosphorus budgets assume that those high concentrations of phosphorus are exported. The Project released 0.1 lbs P per acre in 2024, but the runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field (0.6 lbs P per acre each year) resulted in overall net phosphorus retention, and inorganic nutrient forms were retained (phosphate, nitrate, and ammonium). The vegetation stock was 903 lbs P per acre aboveground and 16 lbs P per acre belowground.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 33 acres of restored wetland, including multiple features: four tile-fed flowthrough pools (A, B, C, G), two of which also occasionally flood from an adjacent ditch (B, G); three depressional pools that function periodically as floodplains depending on water levels in the adjacent ditch or river (D, E, F); and the St. Joseph River. Water enters the Project via three drainage tiles discharging from upstream agricultural lands draining approximately 75 acres adjacent to the north and east of the Project. Water flows through the wetland features and exits into a ditch to the east. The ditch connects to the St. Joseph River, which flows west parallel to the south edge of the Project. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm in which flow is expected from the three input tiles (North, Northeast, Northwest). Floodplain events are defined as periods when water level in the East Ditch or the St. Joseph River exceed their banks and flow into the Project.

Nutrient Retention

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Vegetation at this Project suggests it is possible to have both high nutrient retention and high biodiversity. Managers may consider promoting biodiversity, such as by controlling Cattail or other invasive species, to maximize both nutrient retention and vegetation habitat quality.
- Assess parcel footprint for the ability to capture tile drain, stream, and/or ditch water inputs in order to optimize nutrient input potential (i.e., connectivity).

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Sugarcamp Project, Putnam County

Since construction in 2022, the Sugarcamp Project has received both point source (septic tank) and nonpoint source (tile drain) inflows, which help maintain a consistent water level and nutrient source in the Main Pool even under drought conditions. Throughout 2024, the Main Pool outflow often had no flow, indicating much of the nutrient input was stored and not exported. The Vernal Pool and the hummock and hollow pools are variable in their water storage and resulting potential to retain nutrients. The Project's known nutrient benefit also includes runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source, preventing 0.6 lbs of phosphorus export per acre each year.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology of this Project is passively managed. The Project has 9 acres of restored wetland, consisting of a flow-through wetland system as well as around 50 hummock and hollow pools within a floodplain wetland. The Main Pool has four inflows that flow into the pool before discharging into a ditch flowing into the Blanchard River. Two of the inflows are surface water runoff; one directs water from the hummock and hollow portion of the wetland and the other drains from an agricultural field to the east. The other two inflows are tile drainage from surrounding areas. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event in which the Blanchard River floods its banks filling the hummock and hollow pools.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmfield Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
9 acres	0.6 lbs	19 ± 13 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar flow-through wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Assess parcel footprint for the ability to capture tile drain, stream, or ditch water inputs, in addition to precipitation, in order to optimize nutrient input potential (i.e., connectivity).

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Tipp City Project, Miami County (39.95910, -84.14392)

Since construction in 2022, the main nutrient benefit of the Tipp City Project has been filtering inflows from the Great Miami River. The dry weather conditions of 2024 had relatively limited effect on the volume of water received by the Project, with the year's total inflow volume in 2024 slightly outpacing that of 2023. However, multiple large flooding events over a short period in April resulted in decreased water storage capacity and shorter residence times, likely accounting for the lower nutrient filtration in 2024 (3.7 lbs phosphorus per acre) as compared to 2023 (11 lbs phosphorus per acre). The Project also contributes 0.7 lbs phosphorus per acre each year from runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source, for a total retention of 4.4 lbs phosphorus per acre.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project (10 acres restored wetland) is an off-channel wetland, consisting of a large, permanently flooded pool. Water enters from the Great Miami River via inflow notch and inundates the pool basin. There is no dedicated outflow, but water exits via backflow and likely also subsurface exchange with the river or groundwater. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a flow event when the river discharge rate at the inflow notch reaches approximately 2,627 cubic feet per second, causing river water to flood the wetland pool.

Nutrient Retention

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar off-channel wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- The inflow notch could be lowered to capture flows more frequently from the Great Miami River, but a balance would need to be found between retaining nutrient loads and not inundating the entire Project.
- Vegetation could be planted in the shallower areas of the wetland pool (i.e., elevated flats and around the edge of the pool) as another way to potentially increase nutrient reductions but would require taking into account the appropriate vegetation for expected flooding regime, which may be constrained by sustained drastic changes in water level (i.e., extreme flooding in winter and spring, and drought conditions in summer and fall).

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Trumbull Creek Project, Ashtabula County (41.66180, -80.99040)

Since construction in 2023, the main nutrient benefit of the Trumbull Creek Project has been runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source, preventing approximately 0.6 lbs phosphorus export per acre each year. Little to no “new” nutrient inputs are filtered by this Project because it is in the middle of a watershed divide (Mill Creek, Bronson Creek) and lacks direct connection to nutrient inputs, and neither factor is likely to change. Soil minerals have the capacity to sorb additional phosphate, although some may be released under anoxic conditions. Continued surveillance for transient phosphate release is needed, particularly during mid-winter thaws when anoxic water containing released nutrients may be exported.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 30 acres of restored wetland. Water enters as precipitation and moves slowly across constructed hummock-hollow microtopography towards the outlet at the north of the Project, ultimately flowing into a tributary of Mill Creek in the Grand River watershed. Although water generally flows south to north, there are no discrete flow paths within this Project. The outflow water level control structure is an Agri Drain which maintains the maximum height of the water in the wetland. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as > 0.5 inches of rain within 48 hours as tracked by nearest USGS gage.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmfield Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
30 acres	0.6 lbs	19 ± 13 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in similar isolated wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Assess parcel footprint for the ability to capture tile drain, stream, or ditch water inputs, in addition to precipitation, in order to optimize nutrient input potential (i.e., connectivity).
- If nutrient-laden water source is directed toward the site, adjust water level control structure(s) to maximize water retention capacity and retain limited nutrient inputs (i.e., residence time).
- If a small parcel has limited connection to a nutrient-laden water source (e.g., the primary source of water is precipitation), the project may not contribute substantially to watershed scale nutrient load reduction goals.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Upper Blanchard Project, Wyandot County

Since construction in 2021, the primary known nutrient benefit of the Upper Blanchard Project has been its runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source, preventing 0.7 lbs phosphorus export per acre each year. Meanwhile, connectivity issues have hindered the Project's nutrient filtration potential. As the Project currently functions, even during high flow events where the inflow is greater than the outflow, there is no connectivity between the Main Pool and the Branching Pool. As a result, there is a noticeable difference seen in aerial imagery and chemistry data for nutrient parameters and turbidity between the two pools at this Project, largely attributed to the lack of vegetation in the Main Pool. Water depth at this Project was also slightly lower in 2024 than in 2023, likely the result of drought conditions.

Surface Water Flow

This Project's inflow is passively managed, while the outflow is controlled by a water level control structure located at the west of the property. The Project has 30 acres of restored wetland, consisting of two wetland pools with the Main Pool being fed by an upstream agricultural ditch. During high flow events, this ditch receives both surface runoff and tile drainage from the surrounding fields. Surface water enters the Project via a wide ditch into the Main Pool. This Project also has a large Branching Pool that does not connect to the rest of the wetland pools during ambient flow. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event in which flow is expected through the upstream agricultural ditch.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmfield Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
30 acres	0.7 lbs	20 ± 13 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar flowthrough wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Increasing the amount of vegetation in the Main Pool would not only lower turbidity in the pool but would also aid in the reduction of nutrient concentrations before leaving the Project.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Van Order Project, Henry County (41.48446, -83.90940)

Since construction in 2021, the primary known nutrient benefit of the Van Order Project has been its runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source which prevents approximately 0.3 lbs phosphorus export per acre each year. The Project pools appear to be functioning as intended, holding water during the wet season (late winter to spring) and drying in summer and fall. Capacity of soils to sorb phosphate appears to be increasing across the Project across years, suggesting potential to capture and hold relatively large loads of phosphorus when water/nutrient inputs are present.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 5 acres of restored wetland and consists of eight isolated wetland pools. Pools 1 - 7 receive flow only from surface water runoff, while the southernmost pool (Pool 8) might receive flood water from a nearby agricultural ditch. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event where surface water runoff is delivered to the pools.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmland Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
5 acres	0.3 lbs	10 ± 5 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in similar isolated wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Assess parcel footprint for the ability to capture tile drain, stream, or ditch water inputs, in addition to precipitation, in order to optimize nutrient input potential (i.e., connectivity).

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Walnut Creek Project, Franklin County (39.83290, -82.89184)

Since construction in 2023, the main nutrient benefit of the Walnut Creek Project has been filtration of inflows from Walnut Creek. This Project received a large volume of nutrient-laden water in 2024. However, due to its relatively high elevation inflow notch, the volumes treated were still less than had the notch been slightly lower, as water can only inflow from the creek during extreme high flow events where large quantities of water may overload the ability of the system to remove nutrients. In 2024, the Project filtered 28 lbs phosphorus per acre. The Project also contributes 0.6 lbs phosphorus per acre each year from runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project (17.4 acres restored wetland) is an off-channel wetland consisting of a permanently flooded deep settling pool at the inflow and at the outflow, with seasonally flooded hummocks and hollows connecting the settling pools. Water enters the Project from Walnut Creek via the inflow notch at the north of the Project and exits back to Walnut Creek via the water level control structure (WLCS) at the south. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as an event in which Walnut Creek floods the wetland, possible at discharge of $\geq 1,064$ cubic feet per second.

Nutrient Retention

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar off-channel wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- The stop logs in the WLCS could be adjusted to retain more water inside the wetland during flow events. Increasing the stop log height by just one 18-cm stop log would promote greater residence times and water volume inside the wetland, resulting in more opportunity for nutrient filtration.
- Lowering the inflow notch would allow for more high nutrient concentration summer flows to be received by the Project, potentially supporting greater nutrient filtration. However, this may cause concern with volume capacity of the site where the whole Project would become inundated. A balance would have to be found between capturing more events and not inundating the entire Project.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.

Weisgerber-Pohlman Project, Williams County (41.42940, -84.39900)

Since construction in 2022, the primary known nutrient benefit of the Weisgerber-Pohlman Project has been its runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source, preventing approximately 0.1 lbs phosphorus export per acre each year. Dry conditions in 2024 limited the nutrient filtration opportunity and overall wetland function of the Project, as well as the duration of standing water held in its vernal pools. The capacity of soils at the Project to sorb phosphate remained similar across years, indicating a consistent potential for soils to trap and hold phosphorus when water/nutrient inputs are present.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 70 acres of restored wetland, consisting of five isolated depressional pools and one large floodplain wetland on the north side of the site. The floodplain wetland receives water from the Tiffin River during high flow events, while the isolated depressional pools only receive surface water runoff. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event in which the Tiffin River floods its bank delivering water to the floodplain wetland.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmland Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
7 acres	0.1 lbs	10 ± 5 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar primarily isolated wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Assess parcel footprint for the ability to capture tile drain, stream, or ditch water inputs, in addition to precipitation, in order to optimize nutrient input potential (i.e., connectivity).

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.